

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) catalysed Oxidation of Aliphatic Esters by Bromamine-T in Aqueous Perchloric Acid Medium

R. VIJAYALAKSHMI RAO** and B. THIMME GOWDA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

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Kinetics of ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of four aliphatic esters, viz. methyl, ethyl, n-propyl and n-butyl acetates by bromamine-T (BAT) have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid medium. The reactions followed zero order kinetics in [BAT] and [H⁺] and fractional order in [ester] and [Ru^{III}]. Effects of added Cl⁻ ion and varying ionic strength of the medium on the rate have been studied. The coefficients of rate-limiting steps have been computed at different temperatures by varying [ester] at each temperature. These constants were used to calculate the activation parameters from the Arrhenius plots. The proposed mechanism involves the formation of a complex between ester and Ru^{III} which later disproportionates via a hydride ion abstraction by Ru^{III} in a slow step. Applicability of Taft equation has also been tested.

ESTERS of carboxylic acids are an important class of compounds¹. Hence the reactions involving esters are of considerable interest. In an effort to find out the role of positive halogen species in ester reactions under catalytic conditions, kinetics of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidations of four aliphatic esters by bromamine-T, (*N*-bromo-*N*-sodio-*p*-toluenesulphamide) in aqueous perchloric acid medium have been studied.

Esters, mostly aliphatic simple esters have recently been oxidised by a number of reagents²⁻⁵. Both the catalysed and uncatalysed oxidations have been reported.

Experimental

Bromamine-T (BAT) was prepared by the reported method⁶ and purified⁷.

An aqueous stock solution of bromamine-T (~0.1 mol dm⁻³) was prepared and standardised iodometrically. Stock solutions (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of esters, methylacetate (MA), ethyl acetate (EA), n-propyl acetate (PA) and n-butyl acetate (BA) (E. Merck) were prepared in double-distilled water. Aqueous stock solution of RuCl₃ (Johnson and Matthey) was used. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurements: Kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-zero order conditions with [ester] >> [BAT] (at least by 5-10 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of known amounts of BAT solution (0.0002-0.002 mol dm⁻³) equilibrated at a desired temperature to mixtures containing requisite quantities of ester (0.005-0.05

mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.02-0.10 mol dm⁻³), RuCl₃ (1.0 × 10⁻⁵ - 8.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³) and sodium perchlorate solutions. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric determination of unreacted BAT in an aliquot of the reaction mixture at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-zero order rate constant (*k*_{obs}) was computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within ± 3%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Stoichiometries of BAT-ester reactions were determined in the presence of perchloric acid and Ru^{III} ions by equilibrating varying ratios of [BAT] to [ester] at 308 K. Acetic acid and the corresponding acids were identified⁸ as the reaction products. The acid content in the reaction products was determined by volumetric titration against sodium hydroxide. The carboxylic acids did not get oxidised but aldehydes were oxidised to acids under the present experimental conditions. Hence the observed stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1).

where, R = H, CH₃, CH₃CH₂ and CH₃CH₂CH₂.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study are shown in Tables 1-3 and Figs. 1-4. The rate of oxidation in the absence of catalyst was sluggish but increased considerably with the addition of small amount of RuCl₃ (Table 1d). Hydrolyses of esters were also negligible.

** Present address: Materials Science Division, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-ZERO ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY BROMAMINE-T IN PRESENCE OF Ru^{III} IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

 $I=0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp.=308 K

$[\text{BAT}]_0$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{S}]_0$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ $\times 10^2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$			
				MA	EA	PA	BA
(a) Effect of varying $[\text{BAT}]_0$							
0.2	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.4	2.8	3.3	3.7
0.5	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.9	3.3	3.7
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5
2.0	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.8	3.4	3.6
(b) Effect of varying $[\text{S}]_0$							
1.0	0.5	5.0	1.9	1.7	2.1	2.1	2.3
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5
1.0	2.0	5.0	1.9	3.2	3.7	4.7	5.7
1.0	3.0	5.0	1.9	—	—	—	7.9
1.0	4.0	5.0	1.9	5.4	5.9	6.7	—
1.0	5.0	5.0	1.9	6.5	6.9	7.9	—
(c) Effect of varying $[\text{HClO}_4]$							
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.9	2.0	2.8	3.3	3.7
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5
1.0	1.0	7.5	1.9	2.4	2.9	3.2	3.7
1.0	1.0	10.0	1.9	2.5	2.9	3.2	3.8
(d) Effect of varying $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$							
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	1.5	2.2	2.4	2.6
1.0	1.0	5.0	1.9	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5
1.0	1.0	5.0	4.0	3.6	3.8	3.9	5.1
1.0	1.0	5.0	5.9	4.4	4.4	4.8	6.2
1.0	1.0	5.0	7.9	5.4	4.8	5.5	—

TABLE 2—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY BROMAMINE-T IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Order observed in	MA	EA	PA	BA
$[\text{BAT}]$	0	0	0	0
$[\text{S}]$	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7
$[\text{H}^+]$	0	0	0	0
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.5
Activation parameters :				
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	70.8	77.5	102.2	98.4
log A	10.4	11.6	15.9	15.4
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	68.3	75.0	99.7	95.9
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-11.0	-5.5	14.2	11.9
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	82.5	82.1	83.9	80.5

 TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH OF MEDIUM AND Cl⁻ IONS ON RATES OF Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY BROMAMINE-T IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM*

I mol dm^{-3}	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$			
	MA	EA	PA	BA'
0.2	2.4	2.6	3.1	3.4
0.3	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5
0.5	2.3	2.7	3.4	3.6
0.75	2.4	2.8	3.3	3.5
$\times 10^3 [\text{Cl}^-]$				
2.0	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.6
4.0	2.2	2.9	3.4	3.4
5.0	2.4	2.7	3.3	3.5
7.5	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.4

* $10^3 [\text{BAT}] = 10^3 [\text{S}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 1. Plots of $[\text{BAT}]$ vs time for methyl acetate (MA) and n-propyl acetate (PA); $10^3 [\text{ester}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 1.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 308 K. $10^3 [\text{BAT}]_0$ (mol dm⁻³): (a) 0.5, (b) 1.0 and (c) 2.0.

At fixed $[\text{HClO}_4]$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{ester}]$ (in excess), plots of $[\text{BAT}]$ versus time were linear for all the

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{ester}]$ for methyl acetate (MA) and ethyl acetate (EA); $10^3[\text{BAT}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{Ru}^{III}] = 1.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 3. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{ester}]$ for n-propyl acetate (PA) and n-butyl acetate (BA); $10^3[\text{BAT}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{Ru}^{III}] = 1.9 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

esters at least upto 75% completion of reaction. Typical plots are shown in Fig. 1. The pseudo-zero order rate constants (k_{obs}) computed from the plots were unaffected by the changes in the initial concentrations of BAT (0.0002–0.002 mol dm⁻³) (Table 1a), establishing zero order kinetics in [BAT]. At constant [BAT]₀, [HClO₄] and [Ru^{III}], the rate

Fig. 4. Plots of (i) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{Ru}^{III}]$; $10^3[\text{BAT}]_0 = 10^3[\text{ester}]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^3[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 308 K, and (ii) ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger : (●) methyl acetate, (x) ethyl acetate, (○) propyl acetate and (Δ) butyl acetate.

increased with increase in [ester] (Table 1b) with fractional order dependences (Table 2). The rate also increased with increase in [Ru^{III}] with varying fractional order kinetics in [Ru^{III}] (Tables 1d and 2). But the reactions were independent of [HClO₄] at constant [ester]₀, [BAT]₀ and [Ru^{III}] (Table 1c). The rate was also unaffected by the variation in ionic strength of the reaction medium (Table 3). The ester concentrations were varied at different temperatures and the constants of the rate-limiting steps were calculated at each temperature. These constants have been used to compute activation parameters from the Arrhenius plots (Table 2).

Bromamine-T, like chloramine-T and bromamine-B⁹ is moderately a strong electrolyte and the following equilibria exist in its aqueous solutions, depending upon the pH of the medium :

Therefore, the probable reactive species in acid solutions of BAT are ArSO₂NHB_r, ArSO₂NBr₂, HOBr and possibly (ArSO₂NH₂Br)⁺ and (H₂OBr)⁺.

Under the present experimental conditions, i.e. in the acid range 0.02–0.10 mol dm⁻³, ArSO₂NHBr is the most likely oxidising species.

Electronic spectral studies of Connick and Fine¹⁰ reveal that the species such as [RuCl₅(H₂O)]²⁻, [RuCl₄(H₂O)₂]⁻, [RuCl₃(H₂O)₃], [RuCl₂(H₂O)₄]⁺, [RuCl(H₂O)₅]²⁺ do not exist in the aqueous solution of RuCl₃.

Although the species [Ru(H₂O)₆OH]²⁺ is probable, in the acid medium such a species cannot exist because of the equilibrium,

would lie to the right when [H⁺] is much more than [Ru^{III}]. Further if it were to be the case, one would expect inverse dependence on [H⁺] contrary to the present observations. Non-influence of added chloride ions on the rate (Table 3) rules out the formation of chloro complex ions. It is therefore reasonable to assume that hexa-aquo species [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ is the catalysing species. The rate of reaction increased with increase in electron-releasing capacity of the alkyl moiety. This may indicate that an electron-deficient reactive centre is formed in the transition state. Hence the kinetics of zero order in [BAT] and [H⁺] and fractional order in [ester] and [RuCl₃] may be explained by a mechanism shown in Scheme 1, which involves formation of a complex between the ester and Ru^{III} which later disproportionates via a hydride ion abstraction by Ru^{III} in a slow step.

Scheme 1

Based on Scheme 1, the rate law (11) has been derived.

$$-\frac{d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 k_2 [\text{ester}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{ester}] + K_1 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1 + K_1 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]}{K_1 k_2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \left(\frac{1}{[\text{ester}]} + \frac{1}{k_2 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} \right) \quad (12)$$

$$= \frac{1 + K_1 [\text{ester}]}{K_1 k_2 [\text{ester}]} \left(\frac{1}{[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]} + \frac{1}{k_2 [\text{ester}]} \right) \quad (13)$$

The plots of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[ester] were linear for all the esters with finite intercepts on the ordinates (Figs. 2 and 3) in conformity with the rate law (13). From the slope and intercept of the plot, the formation constant (K₁) of the complex and disproportionation constant (k₂) were calculated, which were also computed at different temperatures by varying [ester] at each temperature: K₁ (308 K): 116.8 (MA), 135.7 (EA), 61.3 (PA), 62.1 (BA). The k₂ values at different temperatures (Table 4) have been used to evaluate the activation parameters from the Arrhenius plots (log k₂ vs 1/T and log (k₂/T) vs 1/T) (Table 2). The plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[Ru^{III}] was also reasonably linear for all the esters (Fig. 4).

TABLE 4—DISPROPORTIONATION CONSTANTS (k₂)^{*} FOR Ru^{III} CATALYSED OXIDATION OF ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY BROMAMINE-T IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM

Temp.	k ₂ (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)			
	MA	EA	PA	BA
308	2.39	2.63	4.78	5.01
318	3.76	4.05	7.52	7.52
318	5.85	7.02	17.5	17.50

* From rate law (13).

The increase in reactivity from methyl to n-butyl acetate (Table 1) could be due to the electron-releasing capacity of the alkyl groups. Thus the hydride ion transfer mechanism is in accordance with the substituent effect. The increase in the electron density on alkyl-oxygen also favours the formation of Ru^{III}-ester complex. The hydride ion transfer mechanisms have been proposed in a number of cases i.e., in the oxidation of aldehydes, ethers and alcohols^{2,3,5,11}.

The negligible hydrolyses or uncatalysed oxidations under the present experimental conditions rule out the possibilities of reaction going through parallel or competitive mechanisms rather than the one proposed.

The difference in ΔS[‡] are lower than the corresponding changes in E_a values and hence the reactions may be enthalpy controlled. This also supported from the values of isokinetic temperature β (1216 K) which is very much higher than the experimental range employed (308–318 K). The β value was obtained from the slope of the linear plot of ΔH[‡] vs ΔS[‡] (Fig. 4). ΔG[‡] values are nearly constant showing the operation of same mechanism with all the esters.

The applicability of Taft equation has also been tested. The following expressions were found to be valid (ethyl acetate showed deviation),

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -1.20 \sigma^* + 0.36 \quad (14)$$

$$\log k_{\text{obs}} = -0.45 E_s + 0.36 \quad (15)$$

A negative value of polar constant (σ^*) indicates that the electron-donating centres increase the rate of reaction. It is also evident from equations (14) and (15) that the steric effects are relatively smaller.

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